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Presence of human Herpes Simplex Virus-1 (HSV-1) DNA sequences in different strains of Salmonella

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Abstract: This is the first report in literature showing the presence of human pathogenic virus, Herpes simplex Virus 1 (HSV1), DNA sequence in different kinds of vaccines as well as wild strains of Salmonella. Salmonella causes a number of diseases in human, animals as well as fishes. HSV-1 is human herpes pathogen known to exist in majority of human beings as latent infection. The use of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) has shown that the DNA sequences of HSV-1 existed in 8 out of 17 DNA samples of Salmonella. The results of genesequencings have shown that these sequences are 98-100% homology to HSV-1 genesequences, which reside in latent associated transcripts (LATs) of HSV-1, but also in the complete genome of HSV-1.

Keywords: HSV-1, Salmonella, Latent, PCR, Herpes.

Salmonella is well known to cause a lot of disorders in human, domestic animals, wild animals, birds as well as fishes. There are many vaccines available on the market for human and animals (14). Moreover Salmonella is being used as a vehicle to develop the recombinant vaccines e.g. Herpes Simplex virus. Oral live vaccines are being used to prevent this micro organism and there are recommendations to use Salmonella as vehicle for vaccines e.g. Influenza viruses, Yersinia pestis etc. (4,7,14). Human Herpes infection including HSV-1 is present as latent infection in majority of human population. Till today Bacteriophages are known to infect the bacteria, but there is no report that human pathogenic viruses are present in the pathogenic bacteria like Salmonella, in spite of the fact that Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) has merged a standard technique to identify pathogens in different kind of probes like blood, serum, culture, tissues etc. in medicine (12).

HSV-1 has two distinct lifestyles: productive infection and latent infection. During the productive infection, there are three major kinetic classes of viral genes, immediately early (IE) also called α , early (E) also known as β and late (L) also called γ (16). Productive infection involves the expression of nearly all viral genes required to produce new progeny virus, where as latency is characterized by the repression of nearly all viral gene expression such that only a series of overlapping transcripts, LATs is detected (2). LATs arise from the RL_(b) repeat segments of HSV genome. The major LAT species are around 1.4 to 2.2 kp nuclear RNAs. These are thought to be stable introns that arise from less abundant 8.5 kb primary transcripts. This is evidence that these later minor LAT species also exist in latently infected ganglion (3).

Co infections of bacteria as well as viruses are well known in medicine. There are sporadic reports of co infections of Salmonella with different micro organisms like Cytomgalovirus (CMV) and *Salomonella typhi* infection in adults in Spain and elsewhere (1, 11). In Holland in 1992, there is a report, where HSV was isolated successfully from the gastroenteritis suffering elderly patients from throat swabs, whereas one was unable to isolate the HSV from throat swabs from Salmonella negative elderly patients without gastroenteritis. HSV caused pulmonary implications (5).

In this publication, we have used PCR method to detect the presence of Human Herpes viruses like HSV-1 in different wild strains as well as human and animal vaccines strains of Salmonella.

Material and Methods: DNA isolation: DNA samples (labelled as S1 to S12) of 12 different poultry vaccines of manufacturer A has been isolated using Nucleospin kit (Macherey and Nagel, Germany). Four isolated DNA samples labelled as S13 to S16 of wild strains of different Salmonella were provided from Institute for Hygiene and infectious diseases of animals, Veterinary Medicine, University Giessen (Germany) through Prof. Dr. G. Baljer. One oral live human vaccine of manufacturer B called as S17 has been bought from local market and DNA was isolated as described already. They were stored at -20 degree until they used further. The names of vaccine manufacturers are not disclosed. The names of strains along with other data are shown in the table 1.

Salmonella specific PCR: All isolated Salmonella DNA were tested with PCR for the presence of Salmonella specific DNA with Genekam Salmonella Kit (Genekam, Germany), which is made according to established method (9). Brief description of method is: One μl of Salmonella DNA was added to 10 μl of 2 x Genekam Master Mix (which contains nucleotides, 0.5 units of Taq, buffers) and 1 μl of 1 pmol forward and backward primers (Microsynth, Switzerland) each in 0.2 ml micro tubes, where total volume was made to 20 μl by adding 7 μl of molecular water. The PCR test was run with positive control of Salmonella and negative control in thermocycler (Biometra, Germany). Later electrophoresis was done on 2% agarose gel (Carl Roth, Germany) with 100 bp marker (Fermentas, Germany) and the results were made on gel soaked in Ethidium bromide (Carl Roth, Germany) under ultraviolet light. The Salmonella specific PCR product was obtained at 284 bp.

HSV-1 specific PCR: Each Salmonella DNA sample was run for PCR for Herpes Simplex virus 1 with Genekam HSV Kit (Genekam, Germany) according to the method (10). Short description of the method: 1 μl of DNA was added to 10 μl Genekam Mastermix (2 x) as well as 1 μl of 1 pmol forward each and backward primers (Microsynth, Switzerland) in 0.2 ml micro tubes. The volume was made 20 μl by adding 7 μl of molecular water. The positive and negative controls were included each time during PCR. In negative control, instead of 1 μl DNA, molecular water was added. The results were done on 2% agarose gel with 100 bp marker and they were visualized from gels soaked in Ethidium bromide under ultraviolet light. The PCR product was obtained at 147 bp, which is specific for HSV-1. DNA samples positive in Salmonella specific PCR were tested here. These primers target RL region of HSV-1 (10).

Cross reaction panel: Conventional PCR test for HSV-1 was checked for the cross reactions with different DNA samples of viruses like CMV, Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV), Varicella-Zoster Virus (VZV), HSV-2, Equine Herpes Virus, Canine Herpes Virus, Feline Herpes Virus, Koi's Herpes Virus etc. as well as bacteria of human and animal importance like *Legionella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pasteurella multocida* along with negative control. This cross reactions panel was done in order to make sure that HSV-1 PCR is highly specific. It was found that the PCR test detected only HSV-1.

The PCR products of HSV-1 positive Salmonella of samples S8 and S13 were subjected to genesequencing with HSV-1 specific PCR primers with ABI 310 genesequencer (Applied Biosystem, USA) after isolation of PCR product with Millipore isolation kit (Millipore USA). The genesequences are shown in table 2. These genesequences are fed in Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) of NCBI, USA. The resulted search and related other data are shown in tables 3 and 4.

All essential precautions were taken during PCR. All steps were done in separate rooms in order to avoid cross contaminations. The sterile pipette tips with filter were used.

Testing of Salmonella for other Human Herpes viruses: The Salmonella were subjected to PCR test according to method described (10) to see whether they are positive for CMV, VZV, EBV and HSV-2. All DNA samples were negative except two non specific bands in CMV.

Results: Before using the HSV-1 specific kit, it was validated with the cross reactions panel mentioned else where, the PCR test has detected only HSV-1. It was unable to detect other viruses like human herpes viruses and other micro organisms as well as there was no band in negative control. The cross reaction panel was made to make sure that HSV-1 PCR is highly HSV-1 specific, moreover it has shown no presence of HSV-1 in other bacteria like Pasteurella, Legionella, Staphylococcus etc as they are negative in HSV-1 specific PCR.

All 17 DNA samples were subjected to Salmonella specific PCR and were positive for Salmonella, where as there was no band in negative control. Later these Salmonella positive samples were subjected to HSV-1 specific PCR. It was found that 8 Salmonella out of 17 probes were positive for HSV-1, where as they were negative for CMV, EBV, VZV and HSV-2 in specific PCR tests.

Genesequences of two HSV-1 positive Salmonella samples number S8 and S 13 were subjected to blast search. The results of blast search as shown in table 3 and 4 shows that these genesequences are 98-100% homolog to followings:

- 1) HSV-1 latency-associated transcript: which region is submitted from Drolet et al (6). The homology is 100%.
- 2) HSV-1 complete genome: It is 100% homolog. It occurred in two different sites.
- 3) HSV-1 latency-associated transcript mRNA: It is 100 % homolog. This region is submitted from Spivack et al (15).
- 4) HSV-1 gene encoding two latency-related proteins, complete CDS: This is submitted through Wechselver et al (17). In this case, the homology is 98%.
- 5) HSV-1 latency associated transcript (LAT): This is submitted through Wagner et al (16). Homology is 98% in this case.

The above mentioned results are generated with one genesequence of S8 (Forward) in Blast.

All genesequences for 2 probes are shown in the table 2. Majority of blast search ended up in 100% homology with HSV-1 sequence except a few, which were 98%.

Discussion: In this paper, it is shown that there is a presence of DNA sequences of HSV-1 in Salmonella. It is the first report in literature indicating that genesequences of a human pathogen like HSV-1 are present in pathogenic bacteria like Salmonella. Both micro organisms are spread world wide and cause disorders in human beings. Salmonella is particularly known to cause a number of diseases along with the food poisoning through out the world in human and animals (14). At the same time, HSV-1 is known to widely spread in human population as this virus is present in latent form (12). In this study, it is shown that the

found genesquences exist majority of time in latent associated transcripts so called LAT along with the presence in the whole genome of HSV-1. There is a lot of research going on LAT of HSV-1 to understand the mechanisms and key components involved in HSV-1 latency at present. Mechanisms of Reactivation of latent form of other human herpes viruses like EBV has been found (8,13). Such investigations may be needed in the case of Salmonella also.

In fact this is an accidental discovery as PCR kits made in our house are being strongly screened for related and non related micro organisms. During the validation studies, HSV-1 PCR test were validated with 3 different DNA Salmonella samples and out of three, two were positive in PCR.

Co infections of different types of micro organisms like bacteria and viruses are well known fact, but till today there is little research done to screen the bacteria for pathogenic viruses during the co infections. Now the molecular tools are available to do such screening to understand the involvement of bacteria in virus infections. As till today transmission of viruses through hosts or vectors like mosquitoes, ticks, animals, human, birds, parasite are well known fact, therefore this paper may like to add a new host or vector for the presence of pathogenic viruses i.e. bacteria better to call Salmonella. There will be need to screen the different strains of other bacteria like E. Coli, Staphylococcus, Campylobacter, Streptococcus, Mycobacterium, Pasteurella etc. for the presence of pathogenic viruses of animals as well as human importance. Moreover there is need of more care to be taken while developing the assays for viruses as they must be screened for cross reactions with bacteria too. Similarly there is need of care to be taken before using Salmonella, E. coli and other bacteria as vector for vaccines or source of recombinant proteins for therapeutic use. This paper may initiate a new era in medicine called medical bacterial virology as there may be a need of careful screening of all bacteria involved during the viral infections.

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Sample number	Kind of bacteria	Kind of strain	Salmonella PCR	HSV1 PCR
S1	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	+
S2	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Vaccine	+	+
S3	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	+
S4	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S5	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S6	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S7	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	+
S8	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Vaccine	+	+
S9	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S10	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S11	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S12	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Vaccine	+	-
S13	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Wild	+	+
S14	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Wild	+	+
S15	<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	Wild	+	-
S16	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	Wild	+	+
S17	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> Strain Ty21a	Vaccine	+	-

Table 1: description and results of PCR of Salmonella samples.

1. S8 (Forward)
CCCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGTGGTCCGA CGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGTA
2. S13 (Forward)
GGGCCGGCTGGAAGACCGCCAGGGGGTTCGGCCGGTGTGCTGTAACCCCCACGCCAATGAC CCACGTACTCCAAGAAGGCATGTGTCCCAA
3. S8 (backward)
CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGTGGT CGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGTA
4. S13 (backward)
CCGGGGGTTCGGCCGGTGTGCTGAAACCCCCACGCCAATGACCCACGTACTCCAAGAAGGCA TGTGTCCCAA

Table 2: Genesequences of 2 samples (S8 and S13).

gb|AF041142.1| Human herpesvirus 1 latency-associated transcript (LAT) gene,
partial sequence
Length=1441

Score = 178 bits (96), Expect = 3e-42
Identities = 96/96 (100%), Gaps = 0/96 (0%)
Strand=Plus/Minus

```
Query 1   CGACACCGGCCGACCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
60
          ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 837  CGACACCGGCCGACCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
778

Query 61   GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   96
          ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 777  GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   742
```

emb|X14112.1|HE1CG Human herpesvirus 1 complete genome
Length=152261

Score = 178 bits (96), Expect = 3e-42
Identities = 96/96 (100%), Gaps = 0/96 (0%)
Strand=Plus/Plus

```
Query 1   CGACACCGGCCGACCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
60
          ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 6673  CGACACCGGCCGACCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
6732

Query 61   GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   96
          ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 6733  GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   6768
```

Score = 178 bits (96), Expect = 3e-42
Identities = 96/96 (100%), Gaps = 0/96 (0%)
Strand=Plus/Minus

```
Query 1
CGACACCGGCCGACCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT   60
```

```
||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 119698
CGACACCGGCCGACCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT   119639
```

```
Query 61   GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   96
          ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 119638  GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   119603
```

Table 3: Result of Blast-request: RID1167741349-15337-156158595516.BLASTQ3

gb|M74421.1|HS1LSSDS Herpes simplex virus type 1 latency-associated transcript mRNA
Length=1982

Score = 178 bits (96), Expect = 3e-42
Identities = 96/96 (100%), Gaps = 0/96 (0%)
Strand=Plus/Minus

```
Query 1   CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
60
          |||
Sbjct 236 CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
177

Query 61   GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   96
          |||
Sbjct 176 GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   141
```

gb|J04323.1|HS1LATRA Herpes simplex type 1 (HSV-1) gene encoding two latency-related proteins, complete cds
Length=3083

Score = 172 bits (93), Expect = 1e-40
Identities = 95/96 (98%), Gaps = 0/96 (0%)
Strand=Plus/Minus

```
Query 1   CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
60
          |||
Sbjct 1126 CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
1067

Query 61   GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   96
          |||
Sbjct 1066 GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   1031
```

gb|M17921.1|HS1LATA Herpes simplex virus type one (HSV-1) latency associated transcript (LAT)
Length=2403

Score = 172 bits (93), Expect = 1e-40
Identities = 95/96 (98%), Gaps = 0/96 (0%)
Strand=Plus/Minus

```
Query 1   CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
60
          |||
Sbjct 431 CGACACCGGCCGACCCCCTGGCGGTCTTCCAGCCGGCCCTTAGATAAGGGGGCAGTTGGT
372

Query 61   GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTGACTAAGGGT   96
          |||
Sbjct 371 GGTCGGACGGGTAAGTAACAGAGTCTAATAAGGGT   336
```

Table 4: Result of Blast-request: RID1167741349-15337-156158595516.BLASTQ3